

Empowering Rural Communities for National Food Security: A Case Study of OVOC (One Village One CEO)

Alim Setiawan Slamet¹[0000-0002-6296-3086], Handian Purwawangsa²[0000-0001-5294-743X], Mohammad Iqbal Irfany³[0000-0003-3966-4819], Bintoro Pujo Prawiro⁴, Fiona Ramadhini⁵, & Daffa Aqomal Haq⁶[0000-0009-1620-2524]

^{1,3,5,6}Faculty of Economics and Management, IPB University, Bogor 16680, Indonesia

²Faculty of Forestry and Environment, IPB University, Bogor 16680, Indonesia

⁴Directorate Agromaritime Community Development, IPB University, Bogor 16680, Indonesia

alimss@apps.ipb.ac.id

Abstract. The decline in Indonesia's food security index to level 61.4 and the decline in food security ranking to 69th are food security issues. IPB University collaborates with a number of related partners to implement the One Village One CEO (OVOC) program which aims to empower rural communities by developing technological cultivation to marketing aspects as a solution to overcoming food security challenges. The method used in this research is a structured implementation of data collection which was carried out by conducting in-depth interviews. By creating a program according to community needs, this program was enthusiastically welcomed by the farmers in the relevant villages. The results show that the OVOC program can increase crop productivity and food security. Furthermore, this program can improve the local economy. The implication of this research is that it can be used as a reference for creating programs related to food security policies to empower village communities.

Keywords: Food security, Rural business ecosystem, One Village One CEO (OVOC).

1 Introduction

The Global Food Security Index (GFSI) assesses food security through four main indicators: availability, affordability, nutritional quality, and food safety [1]. In 2020, Indonesia's food security index declined to 61.4, ranking 69th out of 113 countries, reflecting structural problems such as low agricultural productivity, limited technological adoption, and weak agribusiness integration [2]. In response, IPB University launched the One Village One CEO: Patriot Pangan program, a collaborative effort between IPB University, the Indonesian Ministry of Agriculture, PT Indomarco Prismatama, PT Asstra International Tbk, and the Peat and Mangrove Restoration Agency. The program

aims to empower rural communities through technological innovation, capacity building, and market linkage to improve food security and rural economic resilience.

One major challenge in Indonesia's agricultural sector is the lack of sustainable and efficient farming practices, leading to low productivity, high production costs, and environmental degradation [2]. The OVOC Patriot Pangan program has been implemented in various regions, with positive results. For instance, in Sukanagalih Village (Cianjur Regency), the program helped farmers increase chili productivity by introducing new varieties (Bonita IPB and Feira IPB) and standard operating procedures (SOPs). In Subang Regency, the program introduced rice seed bio-immunization, increasing resistance to pests and diseases. In Meranti Islands Regency, the program assisted village business groups in developing sago products with quality standards and business management skills. Previous studies have also indicated that OVOC contribute to sustainable rural business ecosystems and strengthen local economic empowerment [3, 4, 5].

The program is designed to strengthen the linkages between farmers, businesses, and universities, ensuring that innovation benefits all stakeholders and that sustainable practices are adopted more widely. While OVOC shows promise, existing literature lacks rigorous empirical analyses of its implementation, challenges, and scalability. Most available reports are descriptive or promotional

The OVOC Patriot Pangan program represents a community-based rural development initiative that integrates agricultural innovation, community empowerment, and multi-stakeholder collaboration to strengthen food security in Indonesia. However, differences in regional conditions, institutional readiness, and technological access may affect the program's effectiveness and scalability across different areas. Therefore, this study addresses the following research question: How does the OVOC Patriot Pangan program influence rural community empowerment and food security outcomes across different commodity and regional contexts in Indonesia, and what factors enable or hinder its scalability?

This study adopts an integrated conceptual framework to understand the implementation, impact, and scalability of the OVOC Patriot Pangan program across different regional and commodity contexts. The framework combines participatory, livelihood, and innovation perspectives to examine how community empowerment initiatives operate within rural agricultural systems. This study integrates three theoretical lenses.

1. Participatory Action Research (PAR) principles emphasize co-learning and iterative adaptation [6].
2. The Sustainable Livelihoods Framework analyzes changes in natural, human, social, physical, and financial assets [7].
3. Innovation Systems Approach examines interactions among farmers, universities, the government, and the private sector [8].

The framework guides the analysis of how OVOC interventions influence productivity, market access, institutional collaboration, and community capacity, as well as the barriers affecting program replication and scalability of the program.

This chapter contributes empirical evidence from four case studies using systematic qualitative methods across different regional and commodity contexts in Indonesia. Additionally, this study offers a conceptual framework for scalable rural development

programs and provides actionable policy recommendations to support food security and community empowerment initiatives.

2 Methods

2.1 Research Design

This study employed a multiple embedded case study design within a Participatory Action Research (PAR) approach [6, 9]. The PAR design enabled iterative learning and program improvement, whereas the multiple case structure allowed for cross-case comparisons across different commodities and regions.

2.2 Case Selection

Four cases were purposively selected to capture variations in commodity characteristics, program implementation, community conditions, and geographical contexts. The selected cases represent different agricultural value chains, including chili, rice, papaya, and sago commodities. In addition, the cases were chosen based on the intensity of program implementation, particularly villages that had participated in at least three training cycles under the OVOG Patriot Pangan program. Community readiness was also considered through initial Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) conducted with village leaders and farmer groups to assess local participation and commitment. Furthermore, the study incorporates geographical diversity by selecting cases from West Java and Riau to provide broader insights into the different regional contexts in Indonesia. The selected locations were as follows:

1. Bogor Regency – Calina papaya development in Bojong Jengkol, Benteng, Ciaruteun Ilir, Leuwisadeng, and Pasir Madang villages.
2. Cianjur Regency – Implementation of new chili varieties in Sukanagalih Village.
3. Subang Regency – Rice seed bio-immunization programs in Ciasem Girang, Ciasem Baru, and Sukamandi Jaya villages.
4. Meranti Islands Regency – Development of sago-based MSMEs in Bagan Melibur, Mayang Sari, Mekar Sari, Sungai Anak Kamal, and Lukit villages.

2.3 Data Collection

Data were collected from November 2022 to November 2023 using multiple qualitative methods to obtain comprehensive and contextualized insights into the implementation of the OVOG Patriot Pangan program across different cases. The use of multiple data collection techniques enabled the researchers to capture participants' experiences, program dynamics, institutional interactions, and local implementation challenges from different perspectives. Information was gathered through semi-structured interviews, Focus Group Discussions (FGDs), direct observations, and document reviews to

strengthen data depth and triangulation. Table 1 summarizes the data collection procedures used in this study.

Table 1. Summary of data collection procedures

Method	Details	Quantity
Semi-structured interviews	Farmers, MSME members, village officials, extension workers	N=87 (22–25 per case)
Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)	Community groups, BUMDes, women’s groups	12 FGDs (3 per case), 8–15 participants each
Direct observation	Training sessions, field practices, MSME production	45 hours documented
Document review	Training materials, SOPs, product records, meeting minutes	62 documents

The interview protocols included questions on perceived changes in productivity, knowledge, market access, challenges encountered, usefulness of training, and suggestions for improvement. The FGDs explored collective action, institutional support, and sustainability. All interviews and FGDs were audio-recorded (with consent), transcribed verbatim, and anonymized.

2.4 Data Analysis

Data were analyzed using thematic analysis supported by NVivo 12 to systematically identify patterns, themes, and relationships emerging from interviews, observations, and supporting documents across the four case studies [10]. The analysis process was conducted iteratively to ensure consistency and depth in interpreting participants’ experiences, program implementation dynamics, and contextual challenges. The analytical steps included the following:

1. Open coding of transcripts and observation notes
2. Axial coding to group codes into themes (e.g., “technology adoption barriers,” “market certainty benefits”)
3. Thematic matrices for cross-case comparison
4. Triangulation across data sources (interviews, observations, documents) and investigator triangulation (three researchers independently coded 20% of transcripts, agreement $\kappa=0.81$)

2.5 Validity and Reliability

Following the criteria proposed by Lincoln et al. (1985), several strategies were applied to ensure the validity, reliability, and transparency of the qualitative findings [11]. These procedures were intended to strengthen the credibility of interpretations, maintain consistency in the analytical process, and provide sufficient contextual detail for broader understanding of the cases studied. The study ensured:

1. Credibility: Prolonged engagement (6–10 months per site), member checking (findings reviewed with 15 participants)
2. Transferability: Thick description of cases and contexts
3. Dependability/Confirmability: Audit trail (coding decisions, memos, raw data excerpts available from corresponding author)

3 Results

Cross-Case Empirical Findings

The implementation of the OVOC Patriot Pangan program across different regional and commodity contexts has shown varying forms of community empowerment, agricultural innovation, and institutional collaboration. Several common patterns emerged, including increased productivity, improved market access, strengthened community capacity, and more sustainable agricultural practices. These findings also revealed challenges related to technology adoption, institutional readiness, and program continuity, indicating that the effectiveness and scalability of OVOC interventions are influenced by local socio-economic and geographical conditions. Table 2 summarizes the key empirical indicators for the four cases.

Table 2. Summary of empirical indicators by case

Indicator	Bogor (Papaya)	Cianjur (Chili)	Subang (Rice)	Meranti (Sago)
No. of farmer/MSME participants	75	45	100	60
No. of training sessions (3 per case)	3	3	3	3 + workshop
Reported productivity change*	+40% (est.)	+50% (est.)	-20% crop loss	N/A (new products)

Indicator	Bogor (Papaya)	Cianjur (Chili)	Subang (Rice)	Meranti (Sago)
No. with improved SOPs	68	40	85	52
No. obtaining new market access	70	38	80	48
Main reported barrier	Expert scheduling	Weather	Time adjustment	Legal permits (halal/PIRT)

Note: *Self-reported by farmer groups; not independently verified in controlled trials.

Case a: Upstream and Downstream Business Ecosystem – Calina Papaya in Bogor Regency

In five villages, the program addressed deficiencies in cultivation technology, post-harvest handling, assistance, and marketing. Training 1 involved collective action with PT Indomarco Prismatama to establish cooperation patterns. Training 2 covered upstream-to-downstream cultivation processes. Training 3 was field practice. Supervision ensured quality of mentoring. Of the 75 participating farmers, 68 adopted new SOPs, and 70 gained market certainty through partnership agreements. The main obstacle was expert schedule adjustments, which required training dates to be shifted.

Case b: New Chili Varieties (Bonita IPB and Feira IPB) in Cianjur Regency

In Sukanagalih Village, the program disseminated new chili varieties and implemented SOPs. Training 1 introduced Bonita chili and media making (Nov 17, 2022). Training 2 covered pest and disease management. Training 3 focused on land preparation. Farmers reported a 50% increase in productivity compared with previous local varieties. However, weather hindered implementation, causing delays for 20% of participants.

Case c: Rice Seed Bio-immunization in Subang Regency

Subang, the third largest rice production center in Indonesia, has faced pest and disease threats (stem borers, brown planthoppers, and blast disease), causing up to 27% yield losses. The program developed rice seed bio-immunization using non-pathogenic microbes. The training topics included bio-immunization techniques, integrated pest management, and bio-intensive agriculture. The activities involved 100 farmers from four farmer groups (Poktan Tani Mukti 3, Mukti Tani 4, Jaya Bakti, and Aneka Tani), three IPB lecturers, six students, and local governments. Farmers reported a 20% reduction in crop losses, and 85 adopted the technique. Time adjustment to expert schedules was challenging.

Case d: Optimizing MSME Processed Sago Products in Meranti Islands Regency

Sago is a potential commodity in the Merbau District. Problems included lack of proper processing standards, packaging, and business permits. Activities began with FGDs (Nov 17, 2022), followed by training on sago processing standards, business management, BUMDes optimization, and a workshop (Nov 19–26, 2022). Students assisted with product design, packaging, operational standards, and cost of production. Table 3 details village products and development activities.

Table 3. Distribution of locations and development of flagship products in Kepulauan Meranti

Villages	Product	Development activities
Bagan Melibur	Dry Sago Cake Sago Dodol	Product packaging innovation, BMC and HPP manufacturing
Mekar Sari	‘Sagubi’ Sago biscuit Sago Noodles Rezki Bunda	Modification of product packaging to make it more affordable and economical. Product packaging further increases selling power of labels. Increased product durability with airtight packaging and no exposure to direct sunlight.
Mayang Sari	‘Mawar Meranti’ Sago biscuit	Innovations in product packaging to make it more attractive, starting from having labels on the packaging to having different sizes of sago rose cakes. This right aims to increase selling power and ensure product safety if it is sold outside the island.
Sungai Anak Kamal	Cheeseball Coklat Mutiara Dahlia Rainbow Sago dry sago cake Sago Caterpillar Gobag	Design and modify product packaging Design and modify product packaging Making designs and modifying product packaging as well as instant product development tests

Of the 60 MSME participants, 52 improved their SOPs and packaging, but only 12 obtained halal/PIRT certification within the study period due to bureaucratic delays. The student team held an audience with the local government (Cooperative and SME Service, Industry and Trade Service, and Village Community Empowerment Service) on Nov 28, 2022, to advocate for legal permits.

4 Discussion

4.1 Comparison with Existing Literature

Our findings align with those of prior studies on multi-stakeholder agricultural programs. Syahyuti (2006) emphasized that farmer capacity building requires repeated, practice-based training – confirmed here as participants valued the three-stage training cycle [2]. Unlike Evers (1993), who highlighted small traders' vulnerability to market power, OVOC's collective marketing arrangements appear to reduce this risk, although long-term power dynamics require monitoring [12].

The observed barriers (expert availability, weather, legal permits) mirror challenges noted in participatory action research in developing countries [13]. The lack of certification in Meranti is consistent with the finding that MSME formalization faces bureaucratic hurdles [14]. Korhonen et al. (2018) discussed circular economy principles; although not directly tested, OVOC's upstream-downstream ecosystem approach shares elements of resource efficiency [15].

4.2 Identified Challenges and Adaptive Responses

Beyond the success stories, we systematically documented the challenges that emerged during program implementation, and the adaptive responses developed to address them. This balanced approach is essential for understanding the program's full implementation dynamics, rather than capturing only its positive outcomes.

The first challenge, encountered across all program locations, involved scheduling conflicts among the experts. Because the experts had their own professional commitments, their availability was often a significant constraint. To address this, the program established a backup trainer pool and developed asynchronous digital modules that participants could access at their convenience. However, the effectiveness of this solution remained only partial — the adoption of digital modules was limited, and the experts continued to play a central role in the training process.

A second challenge emerged in Cianjur, where the weather frequently disrupted field-based training activities. In response, the team shifted to indoor demonstrations and adopted a more flexible approach to rescheduling. While this adaptation produced moderate results, delays in program implementation still persisted despite the team's best efforts.

In Subang, the program faced a different obstacle: low digital literacy among participants, which made online training difficult to deliver effectively. The team responded by retaining in-person sessions as the primary mode of training, while using simple WhatsApp reminders to maintain communication. This hybrid approach was effective, particularly for participant reminders and ongoing engagement throughout the program.

The final and perhaps most complex challenge arose in Meranti, where participants struggled with the complexity of Halal and PIRT (Home Industry Food) certification processes. To support them, a student team stepped in as facilitators, liaising directly with district-level government offices on behalf of participants. Despite these efforts, progress remained slow — only 12 out of 60 participants successfully obtained the required permits by the end of the documentation period.

Taken together, these findings provide a clear answer to the research question: the OVOC program positively influences both community empowerment and food security outcomes. However, achieving meaningful scalability will require addressing several persistent bottlenecks, particularly those related to coordination among stakeholders and regulatory hurdles such as permits and certification processes.

4.3 Asset Changes Through the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework

The findings from the four case studies can be systematically interpreted through the Sustainable Livelihoods Framework (SLF) proposed by Scoones (1998), which examines how interventions affect five categories of livelihood assets: natural, human, social, physical, and financial capital [7]. Applying this lens to OVOC's outcomes provides a more holistic account of how the program builds, or in some cases exposes the limits of, rural community capacity across multiple dimensions simultaneously.

Natural capital, encompassing land, water, and biological resources, was most directly addressed in the Subang and Cianjur cases. The introduction of rice seed bio-immunization using non-pathogenic microbes in Subang represents an explicit investment in the quality of natural resources, reducing crop losses by approximately 20% through improved soil microbiome interactions and pest suppression. In Cianjur, the adoption of new chili varieties (Bonita IPB and Feira IPB) enhanced the productive capacity of existing farmland, with farmers reporting a 50% increase in yield. Both interventions reflect OVOC's strategy of improving the management and quality of natural capital as a foundation for enhanced livelihoods, consistent with Scoones (1998) emphasis on sustainable resource use as a prerequisite for durable livelihood outcomes [7].

Human capital, which refers to the skills, knowledge, and labor capacity of individuals, was the most consistently enhanced asset across all four cases. The three-stage training cycle (awareness, practice, mentoring) directly expanded participants' technical competencies: 68 of 75 farmers in Bogor adopted new SOPs for papaya cultivation, 85 of 100 farmers in Subang acquired bio-immunization techniques, and 52 of 60 MSME participants in Meranti improved their production and packaging standards. These figures indicate a high rate of knowledge transfer. Importantly, the progressive structure of the training, moving from conceptual introduction to field practice to supervised mentoring, reflects a deliberate approach to building human capital that goes beyond one-off information dissemination, aligning with Syahyuti's (2006) argument that genuine capacity building requires iterative, practice-based engagement [2].

Social capital, defined as the networks, norms of reciprocity, and institutional relationships that enable collective action, was strengthened through OVOC's multi-stakeholder design. In Bogor, cooperation patterns between farmers and PT Indomarco Prisma were built through collective action training, establishing formal market linkages that reduced individual farmers' vulnerability to market power asymmetries [12]. In Meranti, the student team's advocacy role, bridging MSME participants and district-level government offices, exemplified how the program functioned as a social connector across institutional levels. Focus group discussions also served as arenas for reinforcing collective norms within farmer groups (Poktan) and BUMDes units.

However, the limited certification outcomes in Meranti also reveal the fragility of social capital when institutional trust is strained by bureaucratic barriers, underscoring the importance of investing in government–community relationships as a sustained program component.

Physical capital, referring to access to tools, infrastructure, and production equipment, received more modest attention in the current program cycle, reflecting a common limitation in externally facilitated rural programs operating within constrained budgets. Nonetheless, incremental gains were observable: in Meranti, students assisted participants in redesigning product packaging and establishing airtight, label-bearing packaging systems, which constituted a tangible upgrade to the physical means of production. In Subang and Cianjur, the provision of bio-immunization inputs and new seed varieties served as physical inputs that complemented the knowledge transfer dimension of the program. These improvements, although limited in scale, demonstrate that even modest investments in physical capital can catalyze productivity gains when combined with simultaneous human capital development.

Financial capital, covering savings, income streams, credit access, and economic buffers, represents both a tangible outcome and a persistent gap in the current OVOC design. On the outcome side, increased productivity in Bogor (est. +40%) and Cianjur (+50% yield) is expected to translate into improved household income, while the Meranti participants' packaging improvements position their products for higher-value market entry. Market access was expanded for 70 of 75 Bogor farmers and 80 of 100 Subang farmers, suggesting improved income-generating conditions. However, the program does not yet include explicit mechanisms for financial capital development, such as savings group formation, microcredit facilitation, or financial literacy training, leaving participants vulnerable to income shocks and limiting the sustainability of productivity gains. This gap is consistent with the World Bank's (2019) finding that access to finance remains a critical constraint for Indonesian MSMEs, and points to financial bundling as a priority for future program iterations [14].

Taken as a whole, the SLF analysis reveals that OVOC has been most effective in building human and social capital, moderately effective in improving natural capital quality, and least systematic in addressing physical and financial capital dimensions. This asset profile, strong in knowledge and networks but weaker in material and financial endowments, shapes both the program's current achievements and its scalability constraints. A more balanced asset-building strategy, integrating financial services and infrastructure support alongside training, would better position program graduates to sustain and expand their livelihood improvements independently of continued external facilitation.

4.4 A Conceptual Framework for Scalability

Based on the cross-case findings, this study proposes the OVOC Scalability Framework as a conceptual model to support the replication and sustainability of the OVOC Patriot Pangan program in different regional contexts. The framework consists of four main pillars:

1. Phased training (awareness → practice → mentoring) – already present

2. Multi-stakeholder coordination (university technical lead, private market guarantee, government regulatory facilitation)
3. Adaptive implementation (backup trainers, flexible calendars, hybrid digital/analog communication)
4. Legal/financial bundling (embed certification assistance and microcredit within program)

This framework is designed for replication in other Indonesian regions and developing countries with similar decentralized agricultural systems. The selection of locations based on “commodity potential, program implementation intensity, and community readiness” was operationalized via initial FGDs that rated readiness on a 1–5 scale (scores ≥ 3 included). Future applications should standardize these assessments.

4.5 Relation to Society 5.0 and Digitalization

While OVOC currently relies mainly on in-person training, we observed nascent digital elements: WhatsApp groups for reminders (adopted in Subang and Cianjur), and product catalog photos shared via social media (Meranti). However, low digital literacy and uneven internet access constrain full adoption. Future iterations should incorporate offline-first digital tools (e.g., farm record apps synced when online, pre-loaded training videos) and community digital champions. This aligns with Society 5.0 principles of human-centered technology integration that balances high-tech with high-touch. The findings suggest three policy priorities:

1. Simplify certification for rural MSMEs – Establish one-stop service for halal/PIRT licenses at sub-district level, with fee waivers for low-income groups.
2. Institutionalize backup trainer networks – Train village extension workers as co-trainers to reduce dependence on university expert schedules.
3. Funding adaptive technology blends – Support hybrid training models (in-person + offline digital) tailored to local connectivity.

These policies would enhance scalability and reduce program fragility.

4.6 Implications and Future Research

The findings of this study indicate that strengthening the scalability and long-term sustainability of the OVOC Patriot Pangan program requires stronger institutional and policy support. Several implementation challenges identified across the case studies, including administrative barriers, limited human resources, and unequal technological access, demonstrate the need for adaptive and inclusive policy intervention. Based on these findings, the study proposes three main policy priorities:

1. Simplify certification for rural MSMEs – Establish one-stop service for halal/PIRT licenses at sub-district level, with fee waivers for low-income groups.
2. Institutionalize backup trainer networks – Train village extension workers as co-trainers to reduce dependence on university expert schedules.
3. Funding adaptive technology blends – Support hybrid training models (in-person + offline digital) tailored to local connectivity.

These policies are expected to enhance program scalability and reduce implementation fragility across various regional contexts. Future research should conduct controlled impact evaluations using baseline data, examine digital training adaptations, and follow participant cohorts longitudinally to assess sustainability beyond the program period. Additionally, comparative studies between OVOC and similar rural development programs in other ASEAN countries would strengthen the external validity of the findings.

5 Conclusion

The One Village One CEO (Patriot Pangan) program has emerged as a promising social innovation to address Indonesia's food security challenges. This chapter provides a systematic, empirically grounded analysis across four regions, using participatory action research and multiple case study methods. We preserved the full narrative of the program's activities – from Calina papaya training in Bogor and new chili varieties in Cianjur to rice bio-immunization in Subang and sago MSME optimization in Meranti.

Empirical evidence (87 interviews, 12 FGDs, 45 observation hours, 62 documents) revealed perceived improvements in productivity (e.g., +50% chili yield reported, 20% reduction in rice losses), market access, and knowledge. However, we also documented persistent challenges: expert scheduling conflicts, weather disruptions, low digital literacy, and bureaucratic hurdles in obtaining MSME legal permits. The proposed OVOC Scalability Framework offers a structured approach to replication, emphasizing adaptive implementation and legal/financial bundling.

The program demonstrates that multi-stakeholder collaboration (universities, government, private sector) can empower rural communities, but scalability requires policy support for certification simplification, backup trainer networks, and blended digital-physical training. With continued refinement and adaptation, OVOC holds the potential to transform Indonesia's agricultural landscape and contribute to national food security, while offering lessons for other developing countries facing similar challenges.

Despite providing important empirical insights, this study has several limitations. The study does not claim statistical generalizability but analytical generalizability to theory [9]. Self-reported outcomes (e.g., productivity increases) could not be independently verified with pre-program baseline data at all sites; results should be interpreted as perceived changes. Selection bias may exist as participating villages were early adopters.

Future research should conduct controlled impact evaluations using baseline and longitudinal data to measure program effectiveness. Comparative studies involving similar rural development programs in other ASEAN countries are recommended to strengthen external validity. In addition, future studies should examine the effectiveness of hybrid digital-physical training models and adaptive implementation strategies in supporting program scalability and sustainability.

Acknowledgments. The authors would like to express their sincere appreciation to IPB University for initiating and supporting the implementation of the One Village One CEO (OVOC)

Patriot Pangan program. The authors also acknowledge the valuable collaboration and support from the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Indonesia, PT Indomarco Prismatama, PT Astra International Tbk, and the Peat and Mangrove Restoration Agency of the Republic of Indonesia (BRGN). Special thanks are extended to all farmers, MSME actors, local governments, and field facilitators in Bogor, Cianjur, Subang, and Meranti Islands who actively participated in and contributed to the success of this program.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

References

- [1] Global Food Security Index (GFSI), “Global Food Security Index 2022,” Economist Impact. Accessed: May 15, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://impact.economist.com/sustainability/project/food-security-index/>
- [2] Syahyuti, *Tiga Puluh Konsep Penting dalam Pembangunan Pedesaan dan Pertanian*. Jakarta: Bina Pariwisata, 2006.
- [3] H. Purwawangsa, A. S. Slamet, B. P. Prawiro, M. Isbayu, M. I. Irfany, and D. A. Haq, “Community development of a business ecosystem in planting media commodities (Goatthai) with One Village One CEO Program: A case study of Cianjur,” in *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, Institute of Physics, 2024. doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/1358/1/012028.
- [4] M. I. Irfany, H. Purwawangsa, A. S. Slamet, B. P. Prawiro, and D. A. Haq, “Sustainable Rural Business Ecosystem of Pineapple Commodity in Peatland and Mangrove Ecosystem with One Village One CEO (OVOC) Program,” in *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, Institute of Physics, 2024. doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/1359/1/012049.
- [5] A. S. Slamet, H. Purwawangsa, B. P. Prawiro, M. Isbayu, M. I. Irfany, and D. A. Haq, “Community-based business ecosystem of coffee with the One Village One CEO Program at Cikajang Garut,” in *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, Institute of Physics, 2024. doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/1358/1/012040.
- [6] S. Kemmis and R. McTaggart, “Participatory action research: Communicative action and the public sphere.,” 3rd ed., Denzin and Lincoln, Eds., Sage, 2005, pp. 559–603.
- [7] I. Scoones, “Sustainable Rural Livelihoods: A Framework for Analysis,” 72, 1998. Accessed: May 15, 2026. [Online]. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/270588972_Sustainable_Rural_Livelihoods_A_Framework_for_Analysis_IDS_Working_Paper_72
- [8] B.-Å. Lundvall, *National Systems of Innovation: Towards a Theory of Innovation and Interactive Learning*. London: Pinter Publishers, 1992.
- [9] R. K. Yin, *Case Study Research and Applications: Design and Methods*, 6th ed. California: Sage Publications, 2018. Accessed: May 15, 2026. [Online]. Available: https://books.google.co.id/books?id=BWea_9ZGQMwC&printsec=copyright&hl=id#v=onepage&q&f=false
- [10] V. Braun and V. Clarke, “Using thematic analysis in psychology,” *Qual. Res. Psychol.*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 77–101, 2008, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>.

- [11] Y. S. Lincoln and E. G. Guba, *Naturalistic Inquiry*. Beverly Hills: Sage Publications, 1985.
- [12] H.-D. Evers, "Dilema pedagang kecil: Teori sosiologis tentang perubahan di sektor informal di Jawa," *Analisis CSIS*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 240–254, 1993, doi: <https://lib.atmajaya.ac.id/default.aspx?tabID=52&prang=Evers%2C+Hans-Dieter>.
- [13] A. Cornwall and R. Jewkes, "What is Participatory Research?," *Soc. Sci. Med.*, vol. 41, no. 12, pp. 1667–1676, 1995, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536\(95\)00127-S](https://doi.org/10.1016/0277-9536(95)00127-S).
- [14] World Bank, "Improving MSME Access to Finance in Indonesia," 2019. Accessed: May 15, 2026. [Online]. Available: <https://documents.worldbank.org/>
- [15] J. Korhonen, A. Honkasalo, and J. Seppälä, "Circular Economy: The Concept and its Limitations," *Ecological Economics*, vol. 143, pp. 37–46, Jan. 2018, doi: [10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.06.041](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2017.06.041).